

Data Management Plan

Horizon Europe

Thursday, 18 September 2025

Max Steinhausen¹, Joanna Mau¹, Tobias Conradt², Martin Drews³, Paolo Mazzoli⁴, Pia-Johanna Schweizer⁵, Lydia Cumiskey⁶, Amalie Laursen⁷, Sandro Nanni¹³, Christopher Genillard⁹, Stefan Hochrainer-Stigler¹⁰, Julian Struck¹¹, Levente Huszti¹², Valeria Pancioli⁸, Heiko Apel¹⁴, Katharina Demmich¹⁵, Chahan Kropf¹⁶, Tracy Irvine¹⁷, Sukaina Bharwani¹⁸

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1. TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAET BRAUNSCHWEIG | 10. INTERNATIONALES INSTITUT FUER ANGEWANDTE SYSTEMANALYSE |
| 2. POTSDAM-INSTITUT FUR KLIMAFOLGENFORSCHUNG EV | 11. ERFTVERBAND |
| 3. DANMARKS TEKNISKE UNIVERSITET | 12. ZALA KULONLEGES MENTOK ES ONKENTES TUZOLTO EGYSULET |
| 4. GECOSISTEMA SRL | 13. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA PREVENZIONE, L'AMBIENTE E L'ENERGIA DELL'EMILIA-ROMAGNA |
| 5. RESEARCH INSTITUTE FOR SUSTAINABILITY | 14. HELMHOLTZ ZENTRUM POTSDAM DEUTSCHESGEOFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GFZ |
| 6. UNIVERSITY COLLEGE CORK - NATIONAL UNIVERSITY OF IRELAND, CORK | 15. 52 NORTH SPATIAL INFORMATION RESEARCH GMBH |
| 7. REGION HOVEDSTADEN | 16. EIDGENOESSISCHE TECHNISCHE HOCHSCHULE ZÜRICH |
| 8. AGENZIA REGIONALE PER LA SICUREZZATERRITORIALE E LA PROTEZIONE CIVILE | 17. OASIS HUB LIMITED |
| 9. GENILLARD & CO GMBH | 18. SEI OXFORD OFFICE LIMITED |

Report overview

Project number	101073978
Project acronym	DIRECTED
Project name	Disaster Resilience for Extreme Climate Events providing Interoperable Data, Models, Communication and Governance
Call	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01
Topic	HORIZON-CL3-2021-DRS-01-02
Type of action	HORIZON Innovation Action
Responsible service	European Research Executive Agency
Project starting date	01/10/2022
Project duration	4 Years
Period covered	1 October 2022 - 30 September 2026
Reporting period number	RP1
Periodic report date and version	28 February 2023

Document history

Version	Date	Comment
1.0	03/02/2023	Initial Version (Draft)
2.0	08/08/2023	Updated content based on partner feedback
3.0	18/09/2025	Reworked version for upload to Zenodo

The Horizon Europe Model Grant Agreement requires that a data management plan ('DMP') is established and regularly updated. The use of this template is recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries. In completing the sections of the template the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in Article 17 and analysed in the Annotated Grant Agreement, article 17, must be addressed.

Executive summary

This Deliverable constitutes the Data Management Plan (DMP). This report presents what type of data will be collected, generated or handled throughout the duration of the DIRECTED project and after its completion, not just among the consortium members but also those outside of the project.

The DMP should be considered a living document that is to be updated over the course of the project whenever significant changes arise. Throughout the project more details regarding the structure and types of documents will be clarified and this document will address these changes accordingly. The DMP will be adapted whenever major changes arise or more details become apparent, but it will be reviewed at least annually. A final version of the DMP will be available at the end of the project.

The aim of the initial version of the DIRECTED DMP is to provide a general overview of data types collected and/or created by different project partners and on the usage of such data in line with the project objectives. The Horizon Europe DMP template was used and as the project proceeds, more questions will be addressed in detail.

The DMP states the type of data generated through various work packages (WPs) and the restrictions that may apply during dissemination and exploitation of the data. The DMP outlines the scope of FAIR data management in DIRECTED and the allocation of resources for various activities concerning DMP. The data security measures that apply to the DIRECTED data repositories and the ethical aspects of the data generated through questionnaires and survey are covered in the DMP. The document summarizes the accessibility of the results of various tasks involved from all the WPs. A questionnaire that was circulated among the partners of DIRECTED to obtain information for the DMP is provided at the end of the document as an annex. Generally, it can be said that the data in the project can be categorized as follows:

- Model data including input and output data sets
- Risk-Tandem Framework (set up and evaluation)
- Architecture of the DIRECTED Data Fabric (Data-Infrastructure)
- RWL surveys, interviews and workshops
- Policy recommendations
- Training materials

A large part of the data will be stored in .docx, .pdf, .pptx, .jpg or .xlsx and .csv format according to the data generated. The size of the data stored depends on the data origin and software/user requirements. The largest volume (GB to TB) and greatest number of files have been foreseen for data related to model input (WP 2), whereas other data corresponding to reports and training material are in the range of few MB's and files.

In DIRECTED, data generated and collected throughout the project will be stored in open repositories such as Zenodo or OpenAIRE. A key component of the project is the setup of a Data Fabric (WP 5) to make data, software and metadata generated in DIRECTED publicly accessible and easily findable. Data security of all the restricted data is ensured through access control with restricted access (username + password) to authorized users from each partner. Restricted data is stored locally on existing infrastructure of project partners and on secured self-hosted servers.

Contents

Report overview	2
Document history	3
Executive summary	4
List of Abbreviations	6
1 Data Summary	7
2 FAIR data	9
2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata	9
2.2 Making data accessible	10
2.3 Making data interoperable	12
2.4 Increase data re-use	12
3 Other research outputs	13
4 Allocation of resources	13
5 Data security	14
6 Ethics	14
7 Other issues	14
Annex of figures and tables	16
Annex	17
Partners	19

List of Abbreviations

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
CCA	CLIMATE CHANGE ADAPTION
DMP	DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN
DRM	DISASTER RISK MANAGEMENT
DRR	DISASTER RISK REDUCTION
FAIR	FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND REUSABLE
RWL	REAL WORLD LAB
WP	WORK PACKAGE
DOA	DESCRIPTION OF THE ACTION
GDPR	GENERAL DATA PROTECTION REGULATION

1 Data Summary

The DIRECTED data management plan was prepared based on the official “Horizon Europe data management plan template. The DMP will support DIRECTED partners to identify and address ethics issues and handling of data during and beyond the project’s lifespan. In order to collect input for the DMP, an online spreadsheet was compiled which is stored on the Nextcloud server hosted by TU-Braunschweig that is used by DIRECTED partners to store and share files throughout the project. The file will allow all partners to easily note changes or further details in connection to data management.

DMP and WP 5 – Data Fabric are closely linked in the DIRECTED project. WP 5 has the objective to establish a platform that makes DRR and CCA related data and software accessible and interoperable for users from various communities, e.g. Scientific, administrative, commercial. Further, there is a close link to WP 6 related to dissemination and communication activities. A key task of WP 6 is the establishment of the e-Learning portal where all training materials generated throughout the project will be available. The DMP will describe what data sets should be made available and how. For some aspects the question of how cannot be fully addressed at this stage of the project as this will depend on the outcome of other work packages in the project, namely WP 2.

Sharing of project data is a central goal of DIRECTED, which will in return foster all dissemination and exploitation activity even beyond the duration of the project.

In general, the data generated in DIRECTED can be categorized as follows:

- Model data including input and output
- Risk-Tandem Framework (set up and evaluation)
- Architecture of Data Fabric
- RWL surveys, interviews and workshops
- Policy recommendations
- Training materials

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

A large part of the data generated in the project will be stored as .docx, .pdf, .pptx, .jpg, or .xlsx depending on the type of data generated. Data related to model input or output is stored in different formats such as CSV, TIFF, NetCDF or complex data format such as HDF5.

Will you **re-use any existing data** and what will you re-use it for? What is the **origin/provenance of the data**, either generated or re-used?

Data generated in DIRECTED partially relies on already existing data such as data publications (WP 3) or in case of model input data collected from the RWL, data from national agencies, or monitoring stations are used.

What is the **purpose of the data generation** or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The overall goal of the data generation depends on the different WPs and Tasks in the project. **WP 2** aims to make selected numerical models interoperable, i.e. able to share and incorporate information between various different models. Tools and models used include SaferPLACES Digital Twin Solution for flood risk intelligence, RIM2D pluvial flood risk modelling and forecasting, Seamless Forecasting Tool, CLIMADA, DCAM. Access rights to the tools as well as use of generated output is agreed upon in the CA. Data collected in **WP 3** is largely connected in developing the Risk-Tandem and assessing its functionality in the RWLs. The purpose of the datasets in **WP 4** is to develop and strengthen the Tandem co-production framework.

What is the **expected size of the data** that you intend to generate or re-use?

The sizes of the files vary considerably, whereas simple reports use around a few KB, other files such as static data from an RWL can be up to a size of 40 TB (more than 1000 files).

To whom might your data be **useful** ('data utility'), outside your project?

The data and general research output is aimed at the public, specifically stakeholders of the RWL or policy makers. The generated datasets are of DIRECTED are thus publicly available. Background not intended for public use, is stated in the CA including conditions for availability among DIRECTED partners and how it may or may not be exploited.

2 FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

Most data will, at this stage of the project, will not be assigned a persistent identifier, as these data sets will mostly be for internal use and development. They therefore do not yet require a persistent id. With progressing development of tools, data sets and software more and more data will be made public and receive persistent ids, such as DOI or perma.cc.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created?
What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

Rich metadata will be provided with most openly and internally available data. DIRECTED will make use of one or more of the following metadata standards:

- CERIF - Common European Research Information Format
- CF (Climate and Forecast) Metadata Conventions

In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

For data sets or software where no general standard for metadata exists or where no metadata can easily be attached DIRECTED will ensure that descriptive metadata will be made available as part of the documentation or integrated into the data itself. Metadata will include: title, description, keywords, author, contact, version, date

Where applicable we will also include legal metadata such as licenses and references to work of third parties included in the data or software.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use? Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Keywords will be provided with all publicly available and searchable data sets, software and other publications to improve discoverability. Further metadata will be offered in such a way that it can be harvested

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

For internal use a large part of the data will be stored in the Nextcloud that is hosted on TU-Braunschweig servers. Public data will be distributed directly or through links via the DIRECTED Data-Infrastructure front end and the project website (directedproject.eu). After the project website sizes to exist suitable open access repositories will be found to make this data available. Some project partners may choose to use their own institutional data repositories such as the GFZ data service (<https://dataservices.gfz-potsdam.de/portal/>), SEI's weADAPT platform (<https://www.weadapt.org/>) or on self-hosted git repositories. Git repositories will be the most commonly used way of publishing code to open source tools and software. OpenAIRE will be another repository used by the project partners for data dissemination. Some, but not all repositories considered for data distribution require the presence of a persistent identifier. DIRECTED always aims to adhere the FAIR principal when publishing data and software.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Most data created and used in the course of the DIRECTED program will be made openly accessible. Restrictions to accessibility will have to be made for licensed and sensitive data sets that cannot be made openly accessible on legal and/or ethical grounds. This may include proprietary data in use in the RWLs as well as data that contains priv. Nearly all DIRECTED Deliverables will be publicly available. The only exceptions are deliverables related to WP 8 (Ethics requirements) and internal organization such as the project plan or the Consortium Agreement. All public deliverables will be available on the DIRECTED website for download.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

Internally used data is stored on a Nextcloud instance hosted at TU Braunschweig where user access is controlled through privileges, protected by passwords and can be monitored via access logs.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

To be updated in future versions of the DMP

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

The publication of Metadata is foreseen in WP 5 of the DIRECTED project. With the set-up of the Data Fabric, Task 5.1 foresees the stocktaking of the generated data by all partners. This will be meta data that shall be publicly accessible via the Data Fabric. The data will be hosted on a GitHub and/or GitLab repository. While the details such as deployment or implementation have not been fixed at this stage, it shall be based on open source software such as Python, C++, Java, JS, Rest. The details will be fixed bearing in mind any IPR issues.

Figure 1: Schematic of the DIRECTED Data-Infrastructure developed in WP 5.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?

We are at this stage of the project still in the process of reviewing various data standards and frameworks in respect to their viability for all project members in DIRECTED.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them? To be updated in future versions of the DMP

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

Documentation for the reuse and validation of data created in the DIRECTED project will be provided in academic publications (research papers and data publications), in readme files within code repositories and in code comments. Some tools and software solutions developed or extended in the course of the project will also have dedicated documentation on their own website for online access and or download.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement? Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

A major goal of DIRECTED is to improve the re-usability of data sets and tools for all actors in the DRM and CCA community. In fostering data exchange and communication with regards to disaster resilience, it is key to make knowledge generated by DIRECTED publicly available. For this purpose, WP 5 foresees the establishment of a Data Fabric. Given the early stages of the project, the architecture and infrastructure of the Data Fabric have not yet been decided on.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/13-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards? Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

The provenance of data and code will be documented in the meta data and in the related reports. Our quality assurance process will include a combination of some of the following procedures depending on the character of the data:

- Internal validity checks
- Automated unit testing
- Cross validation
- Benchmarking against other models/predictions
- Validation with observed values/ground truth

Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.

3 Other research outputs

In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).

Within DIRECTED the project partners make use of various tools for collaboration and co-development.

Online collaboration tools such as ClickUp, Miro, and Draw.io are internally used for meeting protocols and digital white boards to support coordination and communication in online meetings. No personal/sensitive data will be shared on these platforms. All access is restricted to project partners and collaborating stakeholders.

Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.

4 Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.)? How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the Horizon Europe grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions) Who will be responsible for data management in your project? How will long term preservation be

ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?

All costs related to FAIR data management that will occur during project implementation will be covered by the project budget. Any other cost that may relate to long term data preservation will be discussed among consortium members. The curation and processing of data for the Data Fabric and its future updates will be defined at a later stage of the project. This also relates to other platforms that publish data and information to the public such as the e-Learning portal. Data management will be overseen by the coordinator TU-Braunschweig.

5 Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)? Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

Data security is of major importance in this project due to its specific nature. Special attention will be given to the security of sensitive data. The protection of data will be ensured through procedures and appropriate technologies. Nextcloud where a large part of the data is stored, offers restricted access via an email and password. Access can only be granted by the coordinator TUBS. This allows for safe storage beyond the project duration. In case it turns out that this is not sufficient, alternatives will be considered throughout the project. These procedures relate to the storage and transfer of sensitive data. The data generated in the project that foresees restricted access to partners and public is handled by the respective partner and stored on their servers.

6 Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics deliverables and ethics chapter in the Description of the Action (DoA). Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

The ethics requirements of the project are covered in WP 8 and included as deliverables D 8.1 – D 8.5: OEI – Requirement No. 1-5. That are due throughout the project. However no ethical issues with the data in DIRECTED are foreseen and all partners will take necessary precautions to prevent sharing data confining to GDPR.

7 Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which ones (please list and briefly describe them)?

UK and Swiss partners in the DIRECTED project operate under EU GDPR regulations in line with all European project partners. No diverting national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures are in place.

Annex of figures and tables

Figure 1: Schematic of the DIRECTED Data-Infrastructure developed in WP 5. 12

Table 1: Annex 1 DMP Questionnaire for DIRECTED partners 18

Annex

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN QUESTIONNAIRE FOR DIRECTED
PLEASE FILL THE BLANK CELLS STARTING FROM COLUMN C FOR THE DIRECTED
PROJECT. IF YOU HAVE MORE THAN ONE DATASET, PLEASE USE ADDITIONAL
COLUMNS.

Table 1: Annex 1 dmp questionnaire for directed partners

PARTNER NAME	NAME
WORK PACKAGE LEADER AND DELIVERABLE LEAD FOR	WP(S)
	PROJECT PARTNER(S) INVOLVED DELIVERABLE (S)
DATASET NAME	NAME
DATASET DESCRIPTION	PLEASE WRITE A BRIEF DESCRIPTION OF THE DATASET
RESPONSIBLE PARTNERS	WHO ARE THE LEAD PARTNERS RESPONSIBLE FOR THE DATASET GENERATION/COLLECTION?
PURPOSE	WHAT IS THE PURPOSE OF THE DATA COLLECTION/GENERATION AND ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT?
TYPE, FORMAT AND VOLUME	WHAT TYPES OF DATA WILL THE PROJECT GENERATE? CAN IT BE STORED BEYOND THE PROJECT, WILL YOU PROVIDE CONSENT?
	WHAT DATA FORMAT IS USED (E.G. XLS, DOC, PDF, PPT, JPEG, OPJ, TIFF, ...)?
VOLUME	WHAT IS THE EXPECTED FILE SIZE (IN GB OR MB)?
	NUMBER OF FILES (APPROX)
SOURCE	WHAT IS THE ORIGIN OF THE DATA? HOW IS THE DATASET GENERATED/COLLECTED?
	WILL YOU PROVIDE META DATA? YES OR NO
	DOES IT NEED ADDITIONAL SOFTWARE TO BE READ? IF YES PLEASE SPECIFY
	DO YOU OR YOUR ORGANISATION HAVE A SPECIFIC WAY OF NAMING A FILE, SPECIFIC USE OF ABBREVIATIONS (E.G. YYYY-MM-DD_FILENAME_AUTHOR.XYZ)
STORAGE AND ACCESS	WHERE DO YOU INTEND TO STORE YOUR DATA?
	DO YOU INTEND TO USE A REPOSITORY? IF YES, PLEASE CLARIFY
	HOW WILL YOU MANAGE ACCESS TO THE DATA?
	WILL DATA BE IDENTIFIED BY A PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER? YES OR NO

EVALUATION OF DATA QUALITY	DO YOU ACCEPT TO EVALUATE THE QUALITY OF DATA PROVIDED ? YES OR NO
	PLEASE DESCRIBE YOUR QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESS
IPR OWNER	DO YOU FORESEE PRIOR INTIMATION BEFORE USING YOUR CONTENT? YES OR NO
	WHICH LICENSE WILL APPLY? PLEASE SPECIFY
	WILL YOU MARK A CONTENT CONFIDENTIAL AS YOU SEE FIT? YES OR NO (SENSITIVE/PUBLIC)
RE-USE EXISTING DATA	WILL YOU RE-USE ANY EXISTING DATA? YES OR NO
	IF YES, HOW WILL YOU USE?
	HOW MANY PEOPLE FROM YOUR TEAM WILL ACCESS THE DATA? ARE THERE SOME SPECIFIC PERSON ALLOCATED FROM YOUR TEAM?
BENEFICIARY	TO WHOM WILL THE DATA BE USEFUL?
ETHICS	ARE THERE ETHICAL ISSUES RELATED TO YOUR DATA? YES OR NO
	WILL YOU TAKE NECESSARY PRECAUTIONS TO PREVENT SHARING PERSONAL DATA CONFINING TO GDPR ?
KEYWORDS	PLEASE PROVIDE SOME KEYWORDS THAT MAY BE ASSOCIATED WITH THE DATASET TO OPTIMIZE REUSE POSSIBILITIES (E.G. SURVEY, ROADMAP, ...)
VERSION NUMBER	WILL YOU PROVIDE CLEAR VERSION NUMBER TO KEEP TRACK OF CHANGES TO THE DATASET? YES OR NO
COSTS AND RESOURCES	IS THERE ENOUGH RESOURCE FROM YOUR SIDE TO ENSURE FAIR (FINDABLE, ACCESSIBLE, INTEROPERABLE AND RE-USABLE) DATA MANAGEMENT AND TIMELY UPLOADING OF GENERATED DATA? YES OR NO
	HOW MANY (PERSONNEL) RESOURCES DO YOU ESTIMATE TO ALLOCATE TO DATA MANAGEMENT (I.E. 1 PERSON MONTH/YEAR)

Partners

